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Continuing Education for Technology Transfer: Time matters.

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this article is to identify and analyse the potential influence of national cultures on the implementation of Continuing Engineering Education training courses, within the context of industrial technology transfer from the perspective of the transferors. Using the example of a Franco-Brazilian programme, which we were commissioned to analyse, our main focus will be to explore how the cultural dimension of time can have an impact on a training course with complex technological contents and high added value. Drawing on Trompenaars' notion of "cultural dilemmas" and that of Demorgon's "adaptive antagonisms", our methodology is based on the analysis of in-depth interviews with French experts

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training Brazilian engineers. The purpose of the present study is to identify the most pertinent profile for international trainers with intercultural competences which combine technological expertise, a broad vision of the industrial and cultural context and strategic planning and vision.

Key words: Engineering education, intercultural training, technology transfer, cultural dilemmas, Brazil, France

INTRODUCTION

Setting up high added value Continuing Engineering Education programmes to accompany technology transfer (TT) of systems, equipment and services, in an international, geostrategic and competitive context is both a sensitive and complex undertaking. In addition, cultural differences, such as variations in the relationship with time, space or people may present additional challenges. The in-house trainers in our study, which was commissioned by the technology provider, are confronted with the complexity inherent in this type of training programme. This can lead to strategic, commercial and technological contradictions. They are also exposed to often unknown cultural dimensions which can both represent additional problems and become indistinguishable from the technical difficulties of the programme. If we consider the anthropological dimension of culture as the “*solution to dilemmas*” [1], lack of knowledge of the clients’ culture can create contexts which can potentially generate further dilemmas in addition to the original technical and human problems [2] [3].

1 TECHNOLOGY TRANSFER AND TRAINING

1.1 The impact of different concepts of time

The aim of this article is to identify and analyse the difficulties linked to differing concepts of time, one of the key elements which emerged during a study of a Franco-Brazilian TT training programme from the perspective of the transferors. These difficulties were often perceived by the engineer trainers with trainees from different cultures as paradoxical or as insoluble dilemmas. At the same time, we aim to distinguish between the different cultural and technical dimensions of the training programme, drawing on Trompenaars’ notion of “*cultural dilemmas*” [1] and that of Demorgon’s “*adaptive antagonisms*” [4] [5]. The use of these two notions can facilitate differentiation between the dilemmas inherent in TT and those linked with cultural differences, while also going beyond the descriptive elements of the “*cultural dimensions*” prominent in the Intercultural Management literature which can lead to overgeneralization.

1.2 The dilemmas of technology transfer training programmes

The objectives, contents and implementation of the TT training programme for Brazilian clients in this study, which is the first of its kind, require the engineer/trainer to adapt to three different elements: the requirements of the French company/employer, satisfaction from the Brazilian clients and the complexity and sensitivity of the technology involved in the transfer. Indeed, the trainer must sell his or her company’s technology, train the clients and explain how the equipment and

systems work but without giving away confidential information or intellectual property. Before embarking on any TT training programme, trainers need to reflect on three imperatives which we identified during the study as: the “*must, will, can dilemma*” [2]. They wonder how far they “*must*” go in transmitting their company’s technological know-how without betraying their trust, how far they are “*willing*” to prepare their client to benefit from the technology autonomously and how far they “*can*” engage in their part time role as trainer, for their main remit remains technology design rather than transmission. Contradictions to do with their role and identities as engineering technologist, business engineer and trainer are thus added to imperatives at three levels (employer, client, technology). Finally, the international context requires systematic use of a foreign language, usually English and exposure to foreign cultures. This is the context, characterized by complexity and tensions, for the training programme for exporting industrial equipment to Brazil, which concerns hundreds of trainee-clients with diverse profiles, jobs, levels and backgrounds, to be trained over several years on sites in France and abroad. In France, the training sessions are in classrooms or directly on-site. The training budget, including logistics and other expenses represents hundreds of thousands of euros. The trainers selected by the company have only had a few months’ preparation between the signature of the contract and the beginning of the training sessions, a time lapse which is considered too short, as we will see later. At the launch of the preparation for the training programme, the very first trainers displayed several different views concerning the duty, the willingness and the capacity of future potential trainers to design, organize and implement this training programme. This can be illustrated by two extreme reactions, firstly from an experienced trainer who had no doubts about the success of the whole of the programme: “*It’s just common sense; each time there’s a new trainee you always have to adapt your message to the population*”. However, the trainer in the second example takes into account that, for many, the programme represents their first experience of a TT contract towards a foreign client, and seems to doubt the capacity of the company to run a training session: *This tightrope between what we can or cannot say.*”

2 ANALYSIS OF A FRANCO-BRAZILIAN TT TRAINING PROGRAMME

2.1 Demorgon’s six perspectives approach

In spite of all the contradictions and imperatives of the programme, the premise of this article is that they will not necessarily lead all the trainers to such insoluble dilemmas. In order to analyse the varying degrees of adaptation we draw on Demorgon’s multiperspectivist approach where dilemmas are posited as “adaptive antagonisms” [4] [5]. Demorgon stresses the fact that situations can be presented as bipolar opposites but along a continuum, where we have to choose to decide and to act according to two or many demands [5]. This notion of adaptation which is culturally informed, chosen, deliberate and singular in each situation completes the notion of “*cultural dimensions*” in the Intercultural Management literature which is often applied as generalisations which can be measured and expressed as figures [6]. Demorgon considers that these cultural dimensions, such as monochrony/polychrony, individualism/collectivism are pre-adaptive antagonisms to any decision or action, allowing, for example a trainer in a multi or monocultural context to act either by “*an immediate action*” or by a “*culturally informed action*” [5]. This “*culturally*

informed action” in every singular situation through “*synchronic adaptation*” operates according to 6 perspectives [3]. These six perspectives include the *field* (religious, political, economic or technological) and the *levels* (individual, corporate and/or national) where cultural interactions take place. Demorgon makes a distinction between what is dependent on *self-organisation or disorganisation* (or dealing with uncertainty) and what is dependent on the *strategy* of the different actors. For example, a company needs a *strategy* which may or may not be culturally influenced, but its members must also be open and adaptable to unpredictable factors or changes which can, in this case, represent cultural or technological dilemmas. For Demorgon, culture is seen as an on-going process which can be changed over time, so *synchronic* intercultural situations should also be analysed from the *diachronic* or time perspective.

2.2 Description of a typical training sequence

The Intercultural Management literature identifies numerous cultural differences [7] which can be reduced to three major categories: relationships with people, space and time. For the purpose of this article we have chosen to focus on time, an aspect which was omnipresent in the interviews conducted with the trainers. Each training session is team-taught by two colleagues or by a hierarchical superior and subordinate. There are intergenerational, interdisciplinary and regional differences among the trainees, who are Brazilian engineers. The teaching team is made up of 26 men and 1 woman and represents three hierarchical levels. The classrooms are organized in rows, as in a formal lecture, and allow little contact with the trainees. Each training sequence, in lecture form, lasts 55 minutes, is pre-timed and limited to a maximum of 70 slides. It is prepared in a sequential and monochronic way with provision for a more polychronic phase of exchange and question and answers at the end. However, the trainees, who have received the slideshow one or two weeks before the training session, can look at the slides on their laptops in the chronological order chosen by the trainer or in any order of their choice, at their own pace. The models, tools etc. have been validated through a contractual process and cannot be modified in class. It is forbidden to use or create any other teaching aid. The presentation is filmed and can be interrupted or even cancelled at any time if the client’s quality manager or a hierarchical superior from the supplying company deems it necessary. The contract specifies that English should be the working language which also has repercussions on the timing of the session, for, apart from some experienced experts, the trainers interviewed stressed the fact that the use of English added extra presentation time, ranging from 20 to 30%. In spite of this precaution and knowledge of the technical vocabulary made possible by a company lexicon with several thousand entries, they also considered there was a risk inherent in the use of the English language in this context.

3 THE INTERVIEWS CONDUCTED WITH TRAINERS

For the interviews with the trainers, given the complexity of technical training for TT, we looked for a training situation which was the most representative, standardised and recurrent as possible within the same training programme. We opted for training sequences implemented during a morning three- hour session with exclusively technological contents, using a lecture format according to the conditions negotiated and contracted between the supplier and the Brazilian client. By signing a

confidentiality contract, we were allowed to observe several sequences of this programme, which allowed us to triangulate the contents of our interviews. These semi-directive interviews with trainers involved in training Brazilian engineers were conducted by three researchers. A total of 102 interviews and coaching sessions were carried out with trainers who were selected from a list of informal networks of both peers and hierarchical superiors. These lists were cross-referenced with the official lists provided by the company's Human Resource Department. The interviews were conducted between 2011 and 2012 on site, near to the informants' workplace. The informants were voluntary and provided with a guarantee of anonymity. Each interviewer followed a guide of seven questions per training sequence. The interviews lasted between 45 and 90 minutes and were recorded, transcribed and analysed.

4 DIFFERENT CONCEPTS OF TIME EXPERIENCED DURING THE TRAINING SESSIONS

In the following section we present three types of classes which reveal cultural dimensions connected with time. We differentiate, in order of complexity between introductory sessions, common core sessions and integrated systems sessions. The introductory sessions of the programme concern general principles and are taught by general engineers with contents which do not have high stakes and represent low industrial, technological or industrial risks. However, the informants were surprised by unexpected interruptions by the trainee/clients during the formal lectures, which is a good illustration of the cultural dimension of polychrony [8]. This situation becomes more complex when the training session deals with the technological problems specific to a common core session. Here it is no longer a question of transmitting more or less abstract knowledge but to transmit contents in the form of problem-solving activities which require a high level of participation from the trainees and reveals new relationships with time.

“For example, typically for the Brazilians you have to be careful (...) they don't use the past. The past for them is now. Everything which is going to happen afterwards is the future. You don't only provide results, you deal with work in progress. It's not because you've done something before. Everyone has their history, everyone has their experience but they are there from now and for tomorrow (...). When you presented your class it's good to say 'I've got 22 years' experience and 19, 000 hours of design'. But that, for them, was before. Now it's how is that going to benefit them. 'I'm going to be able to support you because your needs are to be able to create a system with automated elements which are a little more modern than what you have at the moment and in that phase I'm going to transmit my knowledge which you will be able to transmit to the next people etc. etc.' When the objective is presented like that (...) you can get the Brazilians on board.” (Part-time trainer and expert)

In designing the materials, the trainers take great care to involve the trainees by using a problem-solving approach, “*by dealing with demanding work in progress*”. The ultimate aim is to achieve complete autonomy for the trainees so that they can train their future colleagues in their company in Brazil. This approach reveals cultural dimensions with different orientations to past, present and future [9] [1] which have a direct impact on the delivery of the training programme. In this example, the trainer

tries to gain legitimacy through an experience which can only remain abstract and in which the trainee only sees an individual, professional status and, what is more, from the past. This only has a value if the trainees perceive that it can provide support for their future problem-solving in the immediate present of the sequence. The trainers as providers *must not, will not* and sometimes *cannot* (for strategic reasons or because they *cannot* have a complete overview of the industrial system as a whole) link together the past, present and future of the technological knowledge and know-how of their company without risking giving unauthorised information about experiences or innovations which must remain company property, regardless of the message transmitted to the trainees. Information about the future can only concern content specified in the client's contract and its sensitive character must sometimes remain vague for the trainers themselves, who do not have a global view of the whole system and equipment. On the other hand, the client-trainees try constantly to link past, present and future, in order to obtain information about recent concrete experiences, ongoing productions, or research and development projects so they can plan their own projects and future designs. This tendency for Brazilian culture to closely link past, present and future is confirmed in the literature [9]. This quote also reveals evidence of "*Long term orientation*", or LTO, [6], another time orientation, closely associated with the previous one. This time orientation is not only also a characteristic of Brazilian culture, according to the literature, but reinforces the strategic element of the project which is planned to be implemented over several years. The link to the future, in an immediate present, forces the trainers to become very explicit and immediate concerning their objectives, contents and teaching design.

The second example is of an integrated systems session, which, although it was also designed as a lecture with a sequential and monochronic development, requires polychronic reactions from the trainer. The informants referred to the recurrent difficulty of the trainers who, in the here and now of the session have to have general knowledge of the global equipment system at the same time as highly specialised technological knowledge. In parallel, the trainers must also be extremely reactive to all the questions asked, although the profile of specialist giving priority to a monochronic development of the class in order to explain the technology in detail presents the risk of the expert transmitting too much information or confidential information and no longer being able to respect the timing of the training session.

"We have technological barriers which we have fixed ourselves which mean that we cannot reply to all of the questions. So, there, the trainer deliberately gives a vague answer. The question is asked again. And then finally the trainer is pushed to his limits. And the trainer, he falls down. He falls down literally on the spot, he collapses physically. We've already seen that. The trainer (...) bombarded with questions from the client, fell down. Because there's stress, the wish to do things right and eventually he is pushed to his limits and then he cracks up. So, that's why, during training sessions we systematically have the trainer and the Module coordinator. So that the Module coordinator can support the trainer and if it goes too far he can interrupt the class." (Part-time trainer and expert)

The vast majority of the trainers interviewed highlighted the stress felt during the strictly timed training sessions when they found themselves with the "*must, can, will,*

dilemma” [6] having to reply but not being able or willing to reply to a multitude of questions both general and specific, sensible or incomprehensible, without being able to distinguish between those that came from genuine learning needs or from manipulation.

5 SIX PERSPECTIVES TO ANALYSE THE TRAINERS’ DILEMMAS

Demorgon’s six perspectives theory, at the individual, “*synchronic level*” of the trainer, allows us to distinguish between antagonisms or dilemmas of cultural origin from other “antagonisms”, while revealing the connections between them. For instance, with the cultural dimension of time, in a situation with a monochronic tendency, the trainer will adapt more easily to the “*must, can, will, dilemma*” [2], whereas polychrony, especially if it is experienced as pressure, loss of control and anxiety can transform it into an insoluble dilemma. Demorgon’s theory highlights the fact that a synchronic cultural “*antagonism*” such as polychrony – monochrony can be reinforced by “*strategy*”. In a power struggle between client and supplier the client is less inclined to adapt and can use, consciously or unconsciously, the cultural dimensions which suit him or her for strategic purposes. As we have seen, a group of Brazilian trainee-clients can strategically use polychrony which they culturally manage better than the French trainer, who is also almost isolated, to obtain more information, particularly if the trainer is already limited by contract to a monochronic, pre-arranged training sequence. The strategies used by the trainees are themselves generated and reinforced by the “*globalised, technological, competitive*” activity sector [5] of TT. It is therefore fundamental to know as much as possible about the history of the client’s culture in its “*diachronic perspective*”. In this way, the French trainer can or cannot manage the complexity that Demorgon calls “*self(dis)organisation*” which characterises any international context at an “*individual, corporate and national level*”. This is consistent with research by Lin & Berg [10], who concluded that, while prior international experience on the part of the transferor could enhance TT performance, it could also increase their bargaining power by limiting the flow of technical information.

CONCLUSION

In this article we have highlighted some of the influences of cultural dimensions on training Brazilian engineers by French trainers in the context of TT. We have explored and analysed how the national culture of the trainees can have an impact on the implementation of a training sequence with complex technological content and high added value. Demorgon's six perspectives theory, particularly the notion of “*adaptive antagonisms*” allows us to isolate, observe and analyse the cultural dimensions influencing the interaction. These “adaptive antagonisms” can be of different kinds and represent contradictions or mixed messages in a national, monocultural situation but additional cultural dimensions in an international context. We have concentrated more specifically on the “adaptive antagonisms” linked to time but as we have seen, synchronic adaptation also integrates interpersonal and spatial relationships. The interviews with trainers and our classroom observations revealed the emergence of two opposite and complementary trainer profiles, either implementing a training sequence through “*immediate action*” or “*culturally informed action*”. The coexistence of these two “*antagonisms*” in the training team led the company to set up trainer partners in order to reduce the risk of failure for the client,

the company and the trainers themselves. It appeared that the profile of senior expert with a global view and specialised knowledge was more able to deal with certain “*adaptive antagonisms*”. At the company level, these senior expert trainers, demonstrating a capacity for long-term planning, also tried to participate in the company strategy from the outset of the negotiations for TT. In the contract, they tried to reduce in advance the influence of a training session organised in an exclusively monochronic manner, for they already realized during the negotiations that their Brazilian partners were extremely polychronic. The part-time expert trainers with a stabilised professional ethos seemed more confident in public and more easily able to appropriate the cultural ethos of different countries [3] in complex and difficult geostrategic situations. This led them, in the company under study, to set up very informal networks to exchange good practice. Based on this reflexive practice, it would seem pertinent for them to co-design training programmes for trainers in international contexts including intercultural pedagogy for industry.

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